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Processes of Internationalization in the University with the Participation of Foreign Students

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Abstract

This article presents the problems of the development of higher education in Russia, including the priorities of higher education institutions in the program for the development of competitiveness. Kazan Federal University is considered to be the leader in Russia in the number of foreign students studying in Russia, with more than 7,000 students from 98 countries studying there. Noting that internationalization has become a “universal” phrase that people use to best fit their purpose, we emphasize the need for a more focused definition that sets internationalization parameters if it is to be understood and treated them with importance (Knight & de Wit, 1995).

The main focus of this study is on the study of internal processes of internationalization occurring in the university: 1) The study of factors contributing to and hindering the processes of internationalization; 2) What is internal internationalization in university substructures; its parameters; 3) the practice of social work at the university contributes to the maintenance and development of internal internationalization.

The major method is a survey method conducted among 700 foreign students, aimed at studying the choice of a university by foreign students, studying the factors that contribute to adaptation and hinder adaptation including the internationalization of foreign students.

The key result of this study describes the experience of social practice when working with foreign students and the impact of university activities on internationalization. The internationalization model proposed by the author Schoorman helped to make an analysis of the internationalization process using the example of studying the social life of foreign students.

Key words: internationalization processes in education, criteria for the effectiveness of internal university internationalization processes, foreign students.

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Introduction

The urgency of the problem is connected with the tendency of growth in the last decades of the participation of higher educational institutions in the internationalization process. It is important to form the concept of understanding and its implementation by administrators, teachers and students in a large Russian university, where the mission is to internationalize teaching, scientific research and service aspects of the educational process. By Internationalization (English internationalization), we mean development of techniques that simplify adaptation of foreign students (software, hardware) to the linguistic and cultural characteristics of a region which is different from where the student came from. Internationalization in the practice of social work involves a number of programs and social activities aimed at helping to adapt a foreign student to the realities of a Russian university.

An essential part in ensuring the process of internationalization is the provision of services specific to foreign students, meeting their unique needs. As a rule, they are provided by the offices of international student services. The Association of International Educators (NAFSA) states that the “basic level of services” should include information and assistance prior to arrival, orientation activities, ongoing counseling, protection and intervention, and the development of programs that can improve interaction between students and members of the academic community (Kulman, 1992).

Social practice when working with foreign students and the analysis of university activities, in our opinion, can contribute to the process of internationalization in the University. One of the criteria for measuring the effectiveness of the life and study of foreign students is the social well-being of a foreign student.

An analysis of the literature shows that various foreign and Russian authors study the processes of internationalization from different points of view.

The authors Katz & Kahn view internationalization as an organizational process based on systems theory. Systems theory entails representing organizations as “a complex set of interdependent parts that interact to adapt to an ever changing environment to achieve their goal” (Kreps, 1990, 94). By Albrow and Harari (Harari & Reiff, 1993) internationalization is defined as an educational process that recognizes and reflects the international context of knowledge and practices in which society is viewed as a subsystem of a larger inclusive world. Three aspects of internationalization are highlighted: internationalization as a) a continuous adaptive process b) a comprehensive university-wide process, and c) a multifaceted process.

Katz & Kahn also follow a systems approach and see the organization as an open system, while internationalization is viewed as an adaptation of an educational institution to changes in an increasingly global and interdependent environment (Katz, D. & Kahn, R. L., 1978).

According Pleshakova A., the effectiveness of the process of internationalization of education, we propose to highlight the following socio-pedagogical conditions:

- reliance on cultural, historical and social traditions of Russian education, based on the idea of spirituality;
- increase the level of academic mobility of students and teachers;
- technological readiness of the system of organizing international activities at universities for interaction with foreign universities and work with EU educational programs;
- methodical provision of conditions for successful social and cultural adaptation of students and teachers in the context of academic exchange and their readiness to work in the EU educational programs.

Sergeeva L.V. notes that thanks to international programs university students from different countries enrich their level of intercultural competence. Studying abroad, studying the traditions of another

country and peculiarities of the corporate culture of another university, a student gets an opportunity to look at his own culture, domestic traditions, quality of education in his own university with different eyes.

The development of double degree educational programs is a tool to improve the competitiveness of Russian universities, says M. Pevzner.

Relative indicators of adaptability can be considered as a satisfactory state of health and a sense of spiritual comfort, as well as positive emotions in relationships with others, Vitkovskaya, M.I. notes.

A discourse the author Muravyova conducted on the internationalization of educational programs as a key area of internal internationalization of higher education. The results of the research reveal possible directions and methods of internationalization of educational programs of higher education as part of their modernization, necessary to support changes in the paradigm of higher education caused by external factors, using for this purpose both classroom and extracurricular activities, as well as the potential of the local community and various parties. A typology of the internationalized educational program has been formed, according to the typologies of general programs.

According to Kazantsev V.N. that the trend of modern society in its social responsibility is the internationalization of education. One of the main components of the internationalization process is academic mobility, consisting in international cooperation of universities: exchange programs and internships for students, the organization of joint conferences and schools in the global educational space, the exchange of experience among professional and teaching staff. It is a higher educational institution that is responsible for the future of its nation, educating young specialists and creating new social norms. Modern universities should remember that the system for the internationalization of education is a long and laborious process that will work well when everything is taken into account – a comprehensive program, including the structure as a whole, tasks, functions, methods, means.

Maslennikova covers issues related to the formation of a model of a leading Russian university in the context of the internationalization of higher education, as well as which ideas are at the heart of the modern-world university paradigm. There are factors affecting the implementation of the strategy of internationalization of the educational process. The university which defines internationalization as one of the priority directions of internal development, transcends its own national boundaries, expanding and modifying thereby the educational space it forms. Internationalization allows expanding the number of partner universities, supplementing the curricula of basic educational programs with the necessary resources to improve the quality of the services provided. The orientation of the faculty and student community to world-class education is rightly interpreted by J. Knight as one of the most important benefits that higher education receives from internationalization. Internationalization makes the university the most attractive place to study and work. Students and staff have the opportunity to interact with a large number of people from different cultures and original ideas. This contributes to the creation of new quality of knowledge, which is the main task of any academic community. It should also be understood that each university must implement its own approach to internationalization, based on clearly defined objectives and expected results. Based on the analysis of the definitions of the term “internationalization of higher education”, it can be concluded that in the process of developing internationalization, emphasis should be placed on the internationalization as an educational activity, but not as the university as an economic entity. This reflection is confirmed by such researchers as J. Knight and M. Van der Wende. According to their opinion, internationalization is an innovation in the field of education, a way to improve the quality of the educational programs at large.

Tsareva E.E. considers the problem of the development of multilingual and multicultural students

in the process of internationalization of universities. The author states that the most common manifestation of internationalization is the incoming and outgoing mobility of students, therefore, for full participation in international programs students need not only a good command of foreign languages, but also sufficient knowledge and understanding of the linguistic and cultural characteristics of a foreign culture. In addition, students must show psychological readiness for intercultural dialogue, have tolerance and empathy for representatives of foreign-language cultures. These qualities are part of the multilingual and multicultural competence of students. Multilingualism simplifies the mechanisms of preparation, organization or participation of a university in various international events and conferences due to the students' own potential, which undoubtedly has a positive effect on the international rating of the university knowledge and skills that significantly expand the opportunities for participation in international projects in subjects of the educational process.

Hu Liang Cai shows that the motives for the internationalization of higher education are closely linked to the urbanization process. The internationalization of higher education happens due to the change in existing urban cultural environment during the process of internationalization of the city. The need of society for the socialization in urban cultural space helps to stimulate the process of internationalization of higher education

Kornilova E.V. emphasizes the importance of sociocultural and language adaptation of foreigners in high school. The most important goal of the educational process at the preparatory department is the formation of an active personality, ready to communicate and study with students of different nationalities based on the principles of friendliness towards each other. In the context of the internationalization of higher education, the sociocultural problems of teaching foreign students in Russian universities are becoming increasingly relevant.

Jacky Lumby notes that internationalization has gained great importance in higher education driven by both educational philosophy and commercial imperatives. Cultural change is meant as a related process and as a goal. The author discusses the multifaceted ways in which culture can be perceived and is associated with different orientations to internationalization. Ecology metaphor is used to highlight the dilemmas faced by leaders trying to use cultural exchange as a market product, while they can simultaneously destroy the identity of the cultures on which this strategy is based. It is believed that short «terminism» of people in general and business in particular hinders actions to protect cultural values in addition to their own. The author offers thoughtful and cautious leadership in internationalization, maintaining identity and promoting equality between cultures in the long-term commercial interests of universities, as well as providing individual and public benefits.

Summing up, it is important to note that the above authors study the processes of interiorization from different points of view, external or internal, without showing the mutual influence and interrelations of external macro processes and internal micro processes. Rely on the Shoorman model gives us the opportunity of a holistic review on the internationalization process, which shows the relationship between the organization and the environment. However, the studies of the above authors did not describe the role of the social practice of the university in terms of its influence on the processes of internationalization.

The hypothesis of the study is the undoubted influence of the role of foreign students in the implementation of internationalization and the three assumptions that were confirmed in the course of the study: 1) there are factors that contribute to and hinder the processes of internationalization; 2) Social practice improves the social well-being of a foreign student. The practice of social work at the university contributes to the maintenance and development of internal internationalization; 3) Thanks to the inclusion

in the social practice of different substructures of the university, integration and understanding of the process of internationalization by teachers and the administration of the university takes place.

Method and methodological basis of the study

The scope of the study is determined by the works of Schoorman. He highlights the micro-perspective and the macro-perspective of the internationalization process. The efforts included in the micro perspective of internationalization within the university provide the processes of information support and service management, the development of curricula, individual courses, language courses (Lambert, 1989), study of the host country, participation in international research, internationalization of social events, participation of students in cultural activities, intercultural discussions, cohabitation in hostels.

In the process of questioning, factors contributing to adaptation processes are highlighted. The survey questions are aimed at studying the choice of a university by foreign students, studying the factors that contribute to adaptation and hinder the adaptation of foreign students.

The results of the study

Why do foreigners choose Kazan, Republic of Tatarstan, region of Russia and Kazan Federal University (further – KFU)? The annual growth in the share of foreign respondents who are attracted to RT, above all, by the people living in it (from 46.9% in 2015 to 54,3% in 2017). They are also attracted by the culture of the region (37,9%), its nature (35,3%), and the sights of the city of Kazan (24,1%). Since 2015, the possibility of self-development is important for them – 32.7%, glad that they live here – 72,9% of respondents, in general, satisfied – 16,7%.

According to the KFU 2016, Russia's choice is associated with high quality education, a diploma prestige of 26,3% visit to another country of interest – 19,3%, a cultural one, with an exciting language environment – 16,2%.

According to a sociological survey of 2013, attendance at events and seminars aimed at familiarizing with Kazan and the system of education in Kazan universities contributed to raising awareness of more than 1/3 of interviewed foreign students about Russia and about the university where they study.

The choice of KFU is explained in 2013 – by the combination of the presence of the necessary specialties – 37,5%, with the relative affordable prices of education compared to Moscow and St. Petersburg – 30,4%, in 2016 – by the presence of the necessary specialties and training programs – 30,6%, comfortable student dormitory – 16,0%. There was another interesting factor – a large number of foreign students studying at KFU, including compatriots – 10,7%.

Foreign students see as positive aspect being in a dormitory in a friendly atmosphere towards other each (other students, teachers and neighbors (KFU – 53,8%);

Fig. 1. Dynamics of improving relations with others

Respondents assess the attitude of others to themselves as benevolent (51,6%) or neutral (33,6%) (2013)(Fig. 1).

According to the results of a sociological survey, foreign students living in dormitory speak positively about their neighbors in the hostel, testify the friendly attitude of others (other students, teachers and neighbors) towards themselves – 53,8%. Also in KFU, foreign students have excellent relations with their study groups and with teachers, 52,9%.

A survey of foreign youth showed that the most preferred forms of leisure activities for them are physical training and sports (33,6% of respondents indicated this) and reading (25%) (2017).

According to a sociological survey of foreign students of KFU in the framework of the “TOP 5-100” project in April 2016, 48,7% of respondents like to study in KFU, but «rather like» answered, – 37,0%. Would recommend to study in KFU to others – 59% of respondents.

Every third interrogated foreign student is satisfied with the educational services provided to him in varying degrees (34,5%), and the proportion of those who are not completely satisfied with the quality (“most likely not satisfied” and “not satisfied”) in 2017 is 9, 5% and decreased in comparison with 2015–2016. slightly (no more than 4%). Despite the fact that the proportion of foreign students who are completely satisfied with the quality of educational services received in the Republic of Tatarstan, in comparison with previous periods increased (by 8,5% compared with 2015), only every second respondent in 2017 noted that completely satisfied with studying (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Satisfaction of foreign students with educational services

Factors hindering the adaptation and integration of foreign students

Among the common factors that impede the adaptation of foreign students in Russia weather conditions retain leading position, as noted by two thirds of the foreign students surveyed; every third foreigner (exception – KFU) has difficulties with living in a dormitory. A significant proportion of foreign students find it difficult to adapt to another way of life (24,1%), it is difficult to live in the absence of relatives (22,4%), to communicate in Russian (22,4%) (2017). The peculiarity of students in KFU is more comfortable living conditions – 63,3% fully satisfied in 2015, compared with 50,9% in the whole city of Kazan in 2017. Despite visiting most of the respondents of familiarization programs and meetings about Russia in general and about Kazan, in particular, most of them noted that the greatest difficulty in integrating into the Russian education system is the language barrier (46,4% of foreign respondents from KFU in 2013).

According to the results of a sociological survey the main difficulties for all are the lack of knowledge of the Russian language and difficulties with note-taking lectures. Less than half of the respondents would like to study in a foreign language and most of them are ready to listen to lectures in English. Therefore, further implementation of adaptive modules of basic educational programs (for students in the first year), and the development and implementation of individual courses and modules in foreign languages are necessary.

In general, in the city of Kazan, one of the top-priority problems which is indicated by foreign students in 2017 is to study at the university (41,4%) and looking for a job during their free time (31,9%); at the same time, the problem with studies tends to increase (this was indicated by 37,2% in 2015, 39,1% in 2016 and 41,4% in 2017. But compared to 2016, the number of students concerned about the difficulties of life, the organization of leisure, communication with classmates and other people has gone down.

The problem funding a work during their free time is of great importance, as stated by 31,9% of the respondents. According to a sociological survey, 7,3% of foreign students work, and for them the most important is obtaining professional experience (41,8%), better mastering the Russian language (18,6%), an additional source of income (18,6%). It is good that work for foreign students is significant, they are not willing to sacrifice it to the detriment of their studies, which positively characterizes foreign respondents who are willing to devote 2-3 hours a day for a work, not at school time (KFU – 48,6%).

Actions by the university which should facilitate the process of adaptation and integration of a foreign student

Social adaptation. In order to improve the residence of foreign students, in addition to providing a “Universiade Village” campus that is comfortable by European standards, we have considered the following important points:

- 1) during the settlement in dorms taking into account of religious relations and relations between countries;
- 2) if possible, create more comfortable conditions for living in the hostel of foreign students over 25 years old;
- 3) arrange meetings and assistance in the settlement and paperwork, as well as orientation and domestic consultations of fellow countrymen and foreign activists of student councils;
- 4) living with Russian-speaking neighbors;
- 5) issuing for newly arrived foreign students leaflets in 7 major foreign languages on issues of accommodation, social adaptation, as well as a video clip on cleaning the room with subtitles in 7 languages.

Socio-cultural adaptation includes the following main areas:

- 1) Annual participation of foreign students in KFU events:
 - Birthday of the KFU;
 - Russian Students' Day – “Tatiana's Day”;
 - Student Spring;
 - Events dedicated to the celebration national holidays such as of Victory in the Great Patriotic War of 1941-1945. and etc.
- 2) cultural events organized by foreign students themselves: the Festival of Friendship of Peoples “Colors of the World at KFU”, “Day of Africa”, “Day of the Spring “Navruz Bairam”, Freshmen day for foreign students, “Christmas Eve”, Foreign students “Graduate Day”, etc. Together with the Confucius Institute, the Chinese Culture Festival is held annually as part of the New Year's Eve by the Eastern calendar. All of these activities enables students to widely present their rich culture and traditions, including artifacts;
- 3) cultural events for students of the preparatory faculty, organized jointly with their teachers - “Fresh day”, “Holiday of the Russian language, literature and culture”, “Friendship evening”, etc .;
- 5) active participation in the life and events of their national-cultural communities in the Republic

of Tajikistan, the Youth Assembly of the Peoples of Tatarstan;

6) involvement in the activities of students of the Republic of Tatarstan and the Russian Federation.

7) annual excursions to the museums of KFU, Kazan, trips to the sights of the Republic of Tatarstan.

8) participation of foreign students in events for foreign students in Kazan, Republic of Tatarstan , Russian Federation.

9) organization of sports and other volunteering among foreign students: 77 volunteers took part in the 2013 Universiade, 33 of them - as attachés of the heads of delegations, FINA – 2015 – 23 volunteers, 3 of them – as attachés of the heads of delegations.

10) participation of foreign students of KFU in all major university, city and republican events.

The proportion of foreign students who are aware of events held at their place of study remains stable (77,2% in 2016 and 74,1% in 2017).

Fig.3. Dynamics of growth of participation of foreign students in social events

At the same time, only 44,2% of respondents constantly take part in them (39,4% in 2016), which indicates the potential is still available in this matter.

Over the past 2 years, the share of foreign students who are involved to a certain extent in activities for young people remains stable (in 2016 – 90,8%, in 2017 – 89,5%).

Socio-academic adaptation includes the help of curators to foreign students to establish friendly relations and friendship with Russian students in a group, attracting foreign students to participate in competitions in the Russian language and scientific and practical conferences.

Currently, the following areas of socio-academic adaptation are developed in KFU:

1) Annual participation in the Russian language competition among foreign students in Kazan, in the Olympiad for knowledge of the fundamentals of the legislation of the Russian Federation among foreign students in Kazan and other subject olympiads in Kazan and the Republic of Tatarstan.

2) Development of the service of curators of foreign students in countries in cooperation with public organizations of foreign students of the Republic of Tajikistan.

3) Buddy Program - tutoring of Russian students for students and trainees.

4) The organization of mutual communication of Russian-speaking students with students of the preparatory faculty and interns as carriers of the studied language.

3. Annual participation of foreign students in scientific and practical conferences of the Republic of Tajikistan and the Russian Federation.

Information support. Information support in social networks plays an important role for foreign students. From their they learn the latest news, announcements, documents, conversations, and individual consultations:

1) www.facebook.com/kazanuni,

2) www.twitter.com/kazanuni,

3) https://vk.com/kazan_federal_university – Department of External Relations;

4) [https:// Instagram #kazanfederaluniversity](https://www.instagram.com/kazanfederaluniversity/);

5) https://vk.com/foreign_students – the KFU international friendship club since June 2012;

6) [https:// www / youtube.com / univertv](https://www.youtube.com/univertv) – press service.

Since 2016, information support has been organized for foreign students in all houses of the Universiade Village:

1) Bringing information about events and events.

2) Help in conducting sociological surveys.

Since 2016, programs in the native languages of foreign students on Radio UFM KFU are constantly broadcasted. To date, there has been a release of programs in 16 foreign languages, in which foreign students from 27 foreign countries took part.

Foreign students of KFU participate in all sociological polls conducted among universities of Kazan, the Republic of Tatarstan, and the Russian Federation.

Language service. Includes assistance in the following areas:

1) Help with the translation in solving everyday situations in the dorms University Village in 7 foreign languages (English, French, Chinese, Korean, Turkish, Arabic and Spanish).

2) Classes in the Russian Language Club for foreign students - 2 times a week in the dorms University Village

3) Language clubs in the Universiade Village: English, German, French, Spanish, Chinese – for beginners, 2 lessons per week; Spanish for continuing – 2 lessons per week.

Safety of foreign students. Foreign students of KFU equally note that on the territory of the protected campus leisure facilities and sports facilities (discos, gyms, cafes, etc.) are provided with effective security – 43,9%. Therefore, in future the effective protected campuses of universities should be kept some respondents voice concern that they do not receive information about dangerous places in the city or special dates where / when access to University buildings limited – 39,0% (2013).

The main assistance in overcoming difficulties for foreign students is provided by the international departments of their university, whose work they rate positively, and here both regular general information support and assistance, as well as individual work in the case of a personal appeal, are provided. For a more successful study, 33,1% consider that it is necessary to get more help from the departments focused on working with foreign students. In KFU, according to the data of 2016, the work of the international service is assessed as «excellent» – 43%, «well» – 27% of foreign students.

Work with graduates includes the nomination of the best foreign graduates for the ceremonial presentation of diplomas by the Rector of the KFU, maintaining a database of foreign graduates and communicating with them in social networks.

Based on this, we can conclude that in order to maintain the processes of internationalization, it is necessary to involve foreign students more widely in the practice of social work, as educational support staff, and create a program of social support for foreign students at the university.

Discussion Questions

According to Albrow and Harari, internationalization was viewed as a continuous adaptive process, a comprehensive, university-wide, and multifaceted process. Evaluating the importance of internationalization in terms of the adaptation of an educational institution to changes in the global and interdependent environment, the internal adaptation processes of the university were reviewed in greater detail and in more detail (1992; Harari & Reiff, 1993).

Undoubtedly, the influence of the role of foreign students in the implementation of internationalization and the three assumptions that were confirmed in the course of the study: 1) there are factors that contribute to and hinder the processes of internationalization; 2) social practice improves the social well-being of a foreign student. The practice of social work at the university contributes to the maintenance and development of internal internationalization; 3) thanks to the inclusion in the social practice of different substructures of the university, integration and understanding of the process of internationalization by teachers and the administration of the university takes place.

Social practice is one of the effective ways to internationalization. Due to the inclusion in the social practice of different substructures of the university, the integration and understanding of the process of internationalization by teachers and the administration of the university takes place.

Results

When solving their own problems, foreign students most often rely on themselves (49,1%) or turn to their friends (37,1%). At the same time, 13,8% indicated that in order to solve their problems, they would turn to the management of the school, 6,9% expressed confidence in their teachers, and 7,8% would prefer to go to the Embassy of their country.

For the period 2015-2017 there was a decrease in the share of foreign students who are constantly experiencing financial difficulties (from 21,3% in 2015 to 14,3% and 6% in 2016 and 2017, respectively). Among the main causes of material difficulties, respondents indicated lack of work (44,8%), low wages (33,8%), high prices for food and clothing (19,4%), high education fees (16,4%); at the same time, in 2017 the share of those who indicated high prices for food and clothing as the reason for material difficulties decreased by 9,6% and 13% compared to 2015 and 2016, respectively. The high education fee - by 4,8% and 6,4%, respectively. But the share of those who noted the lack of work as a reason (by 16,6% and 20,6% compared with data of 2015 and 2016, respectively) and the low wages (by 18% and 11,9% compared with 2015 and 2016, respectively).

The factors contributing to and hindering the adaptation processes of foreign students have been studied. Questionnaire of graduates in 2012-2016 showed that they consider examinations and the study of the Russian language as the main difficulties. During the years of study they enjoyed most of all the activities, the studies and practical exercises themselves. As recommendations, they recommend to study hard, engage in public work and actively participate in KFU events, communicate more with friends who

are native Russian speakers.

Conclusion

Since by internationalization we mean development techniques that simplify the adaptation of foreign students, summing up, we can say that the factors contributing to the adaptation of a foreign student are also factors contributing to internationalization.

The described social events held at the university, aimed at helping to adapt a foreign student to the realities of a Russian university, also contribute to internal internationalization.

According to the survey it is clear that the university supports actions that contribute to the processes of internationalization. The Shooman model helped to create a framework for studying the course of internationalization processes in the university with the participation of foreign students.

The following internal processes related to micro-internationalization at the university has been analyzed and identified. These include information support for a foreign student, the work of the international department, the role of language courses, the degree of participation of a foreign student in the cultural life of the university. White spots are revealed in the absence of a foreign student's participation in international studies during the first years of their stay, and individual curricula for foreign students have been little developed.

Social activities aimed at the internationalization of education are widely available in universities and it is one of the effective ways to internationalization. Due to the inclusion in social practices of different substructures of the university, there is an effective integration way of foreign students. This approach is clear and easy to implement by teachers and university administrations, and it is a connecting integrator in the process of internationalization. Social practice improves the social well-being of a foreign student.

The key result of this study is to define the forms of internationalization in the practice of social work, which is proposed as a means to enhance the dialogue between structural units, teachers about conceptualization and the implementation of internationalization in universities.

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